

Open versus Arthroscopic Surgical Management for Recurrent Anterior Instability of the Shoulder: A Prospective Study

Ketan Kumar¹, Chandra Kishor Das²

¹Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Government Medical College, Bihar, India

²Assistant Professor and HOD, Department of Orthopaedics, Government Medical College, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Ketan Kumar

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Abstract:

Background: Recurrent anterior shoulder instability is a common orthopedic condition often treated through surgical intervention. The choice between open and arthroscopic surgical methods remains a topic of ongoing debate, with each approach presenting distinct advantages and disadvantages.

Aim: This study aims to compare the clinical outcomes, efficacy, and safety of open versus arthroscopic surgical techniques in managing recurrent anterior shoulder instability.

Methods: A prospective study was conducted involving 97 patients with recurrent anterior shoulder instability. Patients were randomized to undergo either open or arthroscopic surgery. Data on shoulder function were collected at baseline and follow-up visits using standardized scoring systems. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 21.0, with comparisons made between groups and within groups pre- and post-surgery to assess outcomes.

Results: The study found that both open and arthroscopic surgeries significantly improved shoulder function in patients with recurrent anterior instability. However, the arthroscopic group showed better outcomes in shoulder function scores (ASES and Constant-Murley), range of motion, and had a lower, though not statistically significant, recurrence rate compared to the open surgery group. Complication rates were similar between the two groups, indicating that arthroscopic surgery may be more advantageous for managing this condition.

Conclusion: Arthroscopic surgery for recurrent anterior shoulder instability offers comparable efficacy to open surgery with the added benefits of reduced recovery time and lower postoperative pain. Both methods are viable options, with the choice depending on specific patient factors and surgeon expertise.

Recommendations: Future research should focus on long-term outcomes beyond two years and investigate patient-reported outcomes to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the benefits and drawbacks of each surgical approach. Additionally, developing standardized guidelines for selecting the appropriate surgical method based on individual patient profiles would be beneficial.

Keywords: Recurrent anterior shoulder instability, open surgery, arthroscopic surgery, shoulder stability, prospective study.

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Introduction

Recurrent anterior shoulder instability is a prevalent condition, particularly among athletes and individuals engaged in activities involving significant shoulder movement. This condition arises when the shoulder joint repeatedly dislocates or feels unstable, often due to a previous injury or inherent joint laxity. The instability can severely impact daily activities and quality of life, necessitating effective treatment strategies to restore joint function and prevent further dislocations [1].

Over the years, surgical intervention has become the cornerstone of managing recurrent anterior shoulder instability, especially when conservative treatments fail to yield satisfactory results. Two primary surgical approaches are commonly

employed: open surgery and arthroscopic surgery. Open surgery, the traditional method, involves a larger incision and direct visualization of the shoulder structures, allowing for precise repair of the damaged tissues. However, this technique is often associated with longer recovery times and more postoperative discomfort [2].

In contrast, arthroscopic surgery, a minimally invasive technique, has gained popularity due to its smaller incisions, reduced recovery time, and lower postoperative pain. This technique utilizes an arthroscope, a small camera inserted into the joint, providing the surgeon with a clear view of the shoulder structures on a monitor. Instruments are then used to repair the joint through additional small incisions. Despite its advantages, concerns

about the long-term stability and recurrence rates following arthroscopic surgery persist [3].

The choice between open and arthroscopic surgery remains a subject of ongoing debate among orthopedic surgeons. While numerous studies have compared these techniques, findings are often conflicting, and there is no clear consensus on the superior method. [4] Therefore, it is essential to conduct comprehensive and prospective studies to provide robust evidence on the efficacy, safety, and patient outcomes associated with each surgical approach [5].

This prospective study aims to fill this gap by systematically comparing the clinical outcomes of open versus arthroscopic surgical techniques in the management of recurrent anterior shoulder instability. By evaluating various parameters, including shoulder stability, range of motion, patient satisfaction, and recurrence rates, this study seeks to provide valuable insights that can guide clinical decision-making and improve patient care.

The aim of this study is to compare the clinical outcomes, efficacy, and safety of open versus arthroscopic surgical techniques in the management of recurrent anterior shoulder instability. Specifically, the study aims to evaluate shoulder stability, range of motion, recurrence rates, postoperative pain, recovery times, and overall patient satisfaction associated with each surgical method.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective study design was employed to compare open versus arthroscopic surgical management for recurrent anterior instability of the shoulder.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Government Medical College, Purnea.

Participants: A total of 97 patients diagnosed with recurrent anterior shoulder instability were enrolled in the study.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Inclusion criteria consisted of patients aged between 18 and 60 years, with a history of recurrent anterior shoulder dislocation and positive clinical tests

indicating instability. Patients who had previous shoulder surgeries, significant shoulder arthritis, fractures, or other pathologies affecting shoulder function were excluded from the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive patients meeting the inclusion criteria were enrolled. Randomization was employed to assign patients to either the open surgery group or the arthroscopic surgery group. Blinding of the surgical team was not possible due to the nature of the interventions; however, the data analysis was conducted by an independent researcher unaware of the group allocations.

Variables: The primary variable was the type of surgical management (open vs. arthroscopic). Secondary variables included patient demographics (age, gender), baseline shoulder function scores, number of dislocations prior to surgery, and post-operative outcomes (range of motion, recurrence rate, and complications).

Data Collection: Data were collected using standardized forms at baseline, immediately postoperatively, and during follow-up visits at 3, 6, and 12 months. Preoperative and postoperative shoulder function was assessed using the American Shoulder and Elbow Surgeons (ASES) score and the Constant-Murley score.

Procedure: Patients were randomized into two groups: one group underwent open surgical management, and the other group underwent arthroscopic surgical management. Both procedures were performed by experienced orthopedic surgeons following standard protocols. Postoperative rehabilitation protocols were standardized across both groups.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0

Results

Patient Demographics and Baseline Characteristics: Out of the 97 patients enrolled, 48 were assigned to the open surgery group and 49 to the arthroscopic surgery group. The demographics and baseline characteristics of the patients are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Patient Demographics and Baseline Characteristics

Variable	Open Surgery Group (n=48)	Arthroscopic Surgery Group (n=49)	p-value
Age (years)	35.4 ± 10.3	34.8 ± 9.7	0.75
Gender (M/F)	30/18	32/17	0.83
Number of Dislocations	5.6 ± 2.1	5.8 ± 2.0	0.65
ASES Score (baseline)	42.1 ± 9.5	41.5 ± 8.9	0.72
Constant-Murley Score (baseline)	55.2 ± 10.7	54.8 ± 11.1	0.83

Postoperative Outcomes

Postoperative outcomes, including ASES and Constant-Murley scores, range of motion, and recurrence rates, are presented in Table 2. Significant improvements were observed in both groups, with the arthroscopic group showing slightly better outcomes in shoulder function scores and a lower recurrence rate.

Table 2: Postoperative Outcomes

Outcome	Open Surgery Group (n=48)	Arthroscopic Surgery Group (n=49)	p-value	Outcome
ASES Score (12 months)	85.4 ± 8.2	88.7 ± 7.5	0.04	ASES Score (12 months)
Constant-Murley Score (12 months)	85.1 ± 9.3	89.2 ± 8.6	0.02	Constant-Murley Score (12 months)
Range of Motion (degrees)	165.3 ± 10.5	170.6 ± 8.9	0.03	Range of Motion (degrees)
Recurrence Rate (%)	12.5% (6 patients)	4.1% (2 patients)	0.08	Recurrence Rate (%)
Complication Rate (%)	8.3% (4 patients)	6.1% (3 patients)	0.64	Complication Rate (%)

The study demonstrated significant improvements in shoulder function in both open and arthroscopic surgery groups. The arthroscopic surgery group showed a higher improvement in ASES and Constant-Murley scores ($p = 0.04$ and $p = 0.02$, respectively), indicating better shoulder function. Additionally, the arthroscopic group had a greater range of motion ($p = 0.03$) and a lower recurrence rate of shoulder instability, although the difference in recurrence rate was not statistically significant ($p = 0.08$). The complication rates were comparable between the two groups.

Overall, while both surgical methods are effective for managing recurrent anterior shoulder instability, arthroscopic surgery appears to offer better functional outcomes and a lower recurrence rate compared to open surgery.

Discussion

This study compared the outcomes of open versus arthroscopic surgical management for recurrent anterior instability of the shoulder. The results indicated that both surgical methods significantly improved shoulder function, but the arthroscopic group showed superior outcomes in shoulder function scores, range of motion, and a lower recurrence rate.

The findings of this study align with previous research indicating the effectiveness of both open and arthroscopic surgeries for shoulder instability. However, they also highlight the advantages of arthroscopic techniques, which have become increasingly popular due to their less invasive nature and quicker recovery times.

A study by Mukherjee et al. (2020) found that arthroscopic techniques resulted in higher stability and patient satisfaction compared to open techniques, supporting our results that arthroscopic surgery provides better functional outcomes [5]. Similarly, Hurley et al. (2019) conducted a system-

atic review and meta-analysis which demonstrated that both open and arthroscopic Latarjet procedures yielded significant improvements in patient outcomes, with arthroscopic procedures showing comparable effectiveness to open techniques [6].

Mehdiratta (2021) also reported that both arthroscopic and open surgical techniques were equally effective in managing recurrent anterior shoulder instability, though our study suggests a slight edge for arthroscopic methods in terms of range of motion and recurrence rates [7].

Arthroscopic surgery offers several benefits over open surgery, including smaller incisions, reduced postoperative pain, and faster rehabilitation. These advantages contribute to higher patient satisfaction and quicker return to daily activities and sports. This was corroborated by Hurley et al. (2020), who found that arthroscopic Bankart repair had a lower recurrence rate and higher return-to-play rates compared to conservative management and open surgeries [8].

The lower recurrence rate observed in the arthroscopic group in our study, although not statistically significant, is noteworthy. Previous studies have shown mixed results regarding recurrence rates. Gao et al. (2019) highlighted that newer studies are showing more favorable outcomes for arthroscopic procedures in terms of recurrent instability [9]. Meanwhile, Bottoni et al. (2021) reported similar long-term failure rates between the two methods, indicating that the choice of procedure might be influenced by surgeon expertise and patient-specific factors [10].

The results of this study suggest that while both surgical techniques are effective, arthroscopic surgery may provide better functional outcomes and patient satisfaction. Surgeons should consider the specific clinical scenario, patient preferences, and their own expertise when choosing the surgical

method. Arthroscopic surgery, with its minimally invasive nature and associated benefits, should be favored, particularly in high-demand patients and athletes.

This study had limitations, including a relatively small sample size and the lack of long-term follow-up data. Future research should focus on larger, multicenter trials with extended follow-up periods to better understand the long-term outcomes and potential complications associated with both surgical techniques.

Conclusion

Open and arthroscopic surgeries, both are effective for managing recurrent anterior shoulder instability, but arthroscopic surgery appears to offer better functional outcomes and a lower recurrence rate. This aligns with the growing body of evidence favoring minimally invasive techniques in orthopedic surgery.

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